

D7.1: The State of the Art in Ethics for AR

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ABSTRACT:	This report is the start of a process of guiding end-users in informed decision making about XR technology through a rating system and educational toolbox. In the first step towards this, we employed systematic and scoping literature reviews to examine the current state of XR ethical practices, identify methods for ethics assessment, and review existing XR solutions and their societal implications. The analysis reveals limited diversity and under-reporting of ethical implications in the literature, leading to recommendations for a systematic ethical technology framework and standardized reporting to address these issues in future XR research.
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1. Introduction

This report is the first out of four deliverables of work package 7. The main goal of WP7 is to guide and equip end-users through a rating system and an educational toolbox for informed decision making about the XR technology. The first task in the WP is to consolidate the current state of the art of XR ethical practices in the research and industry. For this purpose, we have employed the systematic literature review as well as a scoping review to map the information.

Our deliverable report is structured in three parts.

In Section 2, we report on a systematic literature review of existing XR research to understand the current state-of-art of the scientific evidence base. Here, we examined issues to the development, deployment, and usage of XR technologies in research environments by documenting the demographics of the people involved in undertaking the research, the characteristics of the participants and information reported by the researchers on ethical issues including privacy, security, and trust. In analysing the literature, we focused on diversity – from the organisations doing the work to the participants engaged, reasoning that XR scientific research needs diversity to ensure that the technology is developed ethically, accurately, and inclusively. We find little diversity in the literature. Moreover, we find that there is a systematic under-reporting related to the ethical implications and considerations of XR technologies, particularly regarding issues surrounding user empowerment.

In Section 3, we identify existing methods that can be adapted for XR assessment of ethics-related aspects, and standards and research efforts (ISO, IEEE, XRSI, etc.).

In section 4 we review current XR solutions such as metaverses, XR portals, development environments as well as XR devices, ethical implications and considerations that arise at the broader societal level from its deployment, and usage.

Collectively, this work provides insights into current standards' limitations and critical gaps in the reporting of key information in the scientific literature and we make recommendations on how to progress these issues through a systematic ethical technology framework and a standardised reporting framework for future research related to XR technologies.

2. Literature Review

We undertook a systematic review of the published peer-reviewed scientific literature on XR (with a specific focus on VR and AR) to understand the state-of-art on a broad range of ethical issues- ranging from the degree to which research in this area is inclusive and diverse, to the extent to which there is explicit reporting of ethical considerations.

We were motivated to examine the scientific literature because, given that most of this work will fall under Technology Readiness Levels 1-7, it can help in gaining insights into the challenges we might face when these technologies become more widely used across society. We reasoned that this activity could provide insights into ethical consequences of XR adoption and allow us to anticipate potential usability issues and accessibility concerns.

In our review, we were particularly interested in documenting the diversity of the participants involved in XR research. Including diverse samples in XR research is important for several reasons. Firstly, it ensures that the research results are an accurate representation of the broader population. Secondly, it is important from an ethical standpoint to consider the implications of XR research, particularly when it involves vulnerable populations. By including diverse samples, researchers can ensure that their studies are conducted in an ethical manner and that participants are treated fairly. In addition to accuracy and ethics, including diverse samples can also foster innovation and creativity in XR research. People from different backgrounds and experiences bring unique perspectives that can inspire new ideas and

approaches. Finally, inclusive research practices can lead to the creation of XR technology that is accessible and beneficial to everyone, regardless of their background or abilities.

There are important lessons on diversity that can be gleaned from examining the psychological sciences literature. The work is dominated by the Western world and certain demographic groups (Henrich et al., 2010). For example, Arnett (2008) illustrated, between 2003 and 2007, almost 70% of samples used in six leading psychology journals were exclusively comprised of Americans and 96% of evidence originated mostly from English-speaking countries. Furthermore, Henrich and colleagues (2010) identified that most psychological research had been conducted on individuals from western, educated, industrial, rich and democratic (WEIRD) backgrounds. Importantly, they discovered WEIRD individuals perceived a perceptual illusion differently to non-WEIRD individuals, suggesting cultural differences may be important in visual perception (Henrich et al., 2010) – a key element of VR and AR.

In addition to this, several studies have identified dimensions of diversity that negatively influence a user's response to immersive technology, yet XR research often overlooks these external factors (Peck et al., 2021). For example, research suggests there are gender differences in embodiment (Gonzalez-Franco & Peck, 2018) and spatial immersion (Kallioniemi et al., 2017). Females are also significantly more likely to experience cybersickness – a variety of autonomic symptoms, such as dizziness, nausea and headache (Kennedy et al., 1993) – compared to males (Munafa et al., 2017; Singla et al., 2017). Despite these differences, one review revealed women were significantly underrepresented in VR research (Peck et al., 2020), however, we note that their search was limited to articles from the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers VR Conferences between 2015 and 2019 and did not include AR research.

In addition to gender, responses to XR vary with age. Studies suggest participants over the age of thirty have a lower sense of embodiment during VR compared to younger participants (Gonzalez-Franco & Peck, 2018), and cybersickness is more common in older adults (Keshavarz et al., 2018; G. D. Park et al., 2006). Moreover, interpupillary distance (IPD) – an important design element in HMDs – increases with age, suggesting children may have difficulty using HMDs designed for greater IPDs, as a mismatch in IPD can cause discomfort, eyestrain and depth perception errors (Hibbard et al., 2020). On a similar note, well-functioning eyes and visual system are required for comfortable use of HMDs. Common vision problems, such as uncorrected refractive errors, stereo- and colour vision deficiency, may impair a user's ability to focus and fuse 3D objects in immersive environments and negatively affect their experience (Pladere et al., 2022). The ability to focus on objects at near decreases with age, requiring prescription correction both for near and distance. The physical design of HMDs are often not compatible with wearing prescription correction (Pladere et al., 2022). Another important factor is ethnicity. The physical design of HMDs is often not compatible with the hair or headdresses of certain ethnic groups (Peck et al., 2021). There is also research suggesting one's ethnicity can influence their sense of presence in VR experiences (Almog et al., 2009).

To date, there have been no systematic investigations on the degree of diversity and inclusivity in XR research. To address this, a systematic literature search was conducted, and articles were analysed in terms of study, participant, and immersive technology characteristics as well as whether, and what, ethical considerations were made explicit in the literature.

2.1 Methods

We focussed our review on work published since 2016 because there have been significant advances in the sector (e.g., in resolution, field of view, dynamic range and correct depth cue (Zhan et al., 2020)) since the Oculus Rift DK2 release in 2013 – widely acknowledged to be a seminal moment in this sector and one that sparked the development and launch of numerous devices to market – including low-budget HMDs compatible with mobile devices (Radianti et al., 2020). The rapid development of HMDs at a lower price, with enhanced visualisation and interaction, has increased the feasibility and accessibility of VR and AR technology. Accounting for the time delays in publication, we reasoned that 2016 would provide a reasonable amount of time for work making use of this technology and other competitors to filter through to the published literature.

2.1.1 Literature Search

A systematic literature search was conducted on the following databases: PsycINFO, Ovid MEDLINE and Embase. The last search was conducted on 20th January 2023. Articles were collected from November 2016 to January 2023. Table S1 shows the combination of keywords used in the search strategy. An initial search also included the keywords 'VR', 'AR' and 'XR', however, they were removed due to producing an excessive number of irrelevant articles. Only full-text articles published in peer-reviewed journals and available in English language were selected for this review. Articles were also limited to those which used human subjects and contained an abstract.

2.1.2 Selection Process

The initial search yielded a total of 1,696 studies. After the removal of duplicates, 1,270 studies underwent title and abstract screening against the eligibility criteria. Following this, 964 studies were excluded, leaving 306 full-text articles to be assessed. During this stage, 181 studies were removed due to the following reasons: no or unclear use of HMD (we chose to focus exclusively on HMDs and exclude other technologies e.g. phone-based XR systems because HMDs are designed specifically for XR applications and by concentrating on HMDs we aimed to reflect the latest advancements in XR technology, given that the majority of development and innovation in the industry is geared towards this segment); the study was not designed in any way that could augment human behaviour and/or performance; the study was a review article, systematic review, or study protocol; no full text was available; the study used animals. A final sample of 125 studies were included in the full review (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Study Selection Process

2.2 General Study Characteristics

One hundred and twenty-five studies were identified from November 2016 to January 2023. Within these studies, 133 individual experiments were identified. Of these, 122 used VR and 11 used AR. Figure 2A presents the number of studies conducted each year. From 2016 up to 2021, there has been a steady increase in VR and AR studies understanding and augmenting human behaviour. Notably, the number of studies declined in 2022- which may be attributable to the COVID-19 pandemic.

2.2.1 Author Location

Overall, 37% of first authors were in the USA ($n=49$), followed by 11% in the United Kingdom (UK; $n=14$), 7% in Canada ($n=9$), 6% in South Korea ($n=8$) and 5% in Switzerland ($n=7$). Similarly, 36% of last authors were in the USA ($n=50$), followed by 11% in the UK ($n=15$), 7% in Canada ($n=9$), 5% in Switzerland ($n=7$) and 5% in South Korea ($n=7$). The top 10 most frequent locations can be seen in Figure 2B. The results indicate over one third of first and last authors were in the USA, whilst most other countries accounted for less than 10% of authors. Importantly, no first or last authors were in South American countries and only 1% of last authors were located in an African country. This provides evidence of a Western bias amongst authors in VR and AR research which is consistent with trends observed in psychological research (Thalmayer et al., 2021).

Figure 2: (A) Number of studies included in review by Year; (B) Top 10 most frequent location of Countries where the included XR research was carried out; (C) Top 5 manufacturer devices used in included studies.

Figure 2C shows the top 5 manufacturer devices used in the experiments. Excluding 7% of studies which did not specify the HMD type ($n=9$), 33% used Oculus devices ($n=42$), 26% used HTC Vive ($n=33$), 13% used Samsung Gear VR ($n=17$), 6% used Microsoft HoloLens ($n=8$), 4% used eMagin ($n=5$), 3% nVisor ($n=4$), 2% Merge VR ($n=2$) and 2% Google Cardboard ($n=2$). A further 11% of experiments used HMDs which were only accounted for once ($n=14$). Although high-end HMD equipment was most frequently used, the data illustrates the variety of accessible HMDs used in the literature.

Sampling Methodology

Excluding 26% of experiments that did not specify their recruitment method ($n=35$), almost all experiments used opportunity sampling (96%, $n=94$), a non-probability sampling technique in which participants are selected based on their availability and willingness to participate in a study. The remaining studies used purposive sampling (4%, $n=4$), also a non-probability sampling technique, but in which

participants are selected based on specific criteria or characteristics that are relevant to the research question. While both methods are non-probability sampling techniques and do not provide a representative sample of the population (Etikan, 2016), purposive sampling allows for more intentional and focused selection of participants, while opportunistic sampling is more based on convenience and availability. In terms of remuneration, 81% did not specify this ($n=108$). Of the remaining experiments, 32% offered financial compensation ($n=8$), 24% offered course credit ($n=6$), 8% offered financial or course credit ($n=2$), 20% offered other compensation (e.g., gift; $n=5$) and 16% did not remunerate participants ($n=4$). The data shows financial rewards were the most common type of remuneration, indicating that studies may have attracted certain individuals that respond in certain ways, possibly biasing the research findings. Note, however, most studies failed to report on this.

2.3 . Sample Characteristics

Of the studies, 80% reported data on age ($n=106$), 82% reported gender ($n=109$), 23% reported ethnicity ($n=31$), 24% indicated visual status ($n=32$), 61% indicated education level ($n=81$) and 95% indicated the location of recruitment ($n=127$; see Figure 5). In total, 7,117 individuals participated in the experiments. Sample sizes ranged from 1 to 208 ($M=53.51$, $SD=45.15$). The distribution is displayed in Figure 6 (skewness = 1.35, kurtosis = 1.67). The data is positively skewed and has a leptokurtic distribution; most sample sizes consisted of up to 54 participants and a fair number of samples included up to 100, but few studies sampled over 100 participants. Considering the time, space and expertise required to use VR and AR technology, study sample sizes were generally good, with studies testing 54 participants on average. However, there was considerable variation across studies, indicating VR and AR research must practice using larger samples more consistently.

Participants were aged between 4 and 94 years ($M=33.07$; $SD=16.41$). The data are moderately skewed and leptokurtic (skewness = 0.81, kurtosis = 0.32) indicating most samples used participants aged between 23 and 32 years. This pattern can be seen in Figure 3B which presents the mean age and standard deviation of participants in studies which reported this information (59%, $n=78$). The figure shows that although XR research sampled a wide age range, most studies used participants aged just below 20 to approximately 50, and fewer studies examined children, adolescents, and older adults above the age of 60. This corresponds with research illustrating that XR technology has been used extensively within occupations for learning and training, such as engineering and medicine (Suh & Prophet, 2018), and may indicate why young adults were most frequently sampled.

Gender diversity across individual studies can be seen in Figure 3D. We calculated the proportion of gender differences such that a score of 1 would represent a fully male sample and a score of 0 would represent a fully female sample. Although gender was represented equally overall ($M=0.50$, $SD=0.23$), on an individual study level, some study samples were heavily biased towards males or females. Three studies used a male-only sample (Bailey, 2022; Meindl et al., 2019; W. Park et al., 2021) and two studies used female only samples, but noted that this was because they required pregnant participants to address their research questions (Frey et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2020).

We also explored the degree to which the data were biased towards Western societies by quantifying the cultural distance of the location of the studies using the Cultural Fixation Index CF_{ST} tool (Figure 3B). We calculated the cultural distance of the studies in our sample relative to the United States of America as it is overwhelmingly the most represented country in science at large (Henrich et al., 2010) and the same is true for our sample (see Figure 2B).

Figure 3: (A) Sample size distribution across the studies; (B) Mean Age and Standard Deviation across Studies. Each tick on the x axis represents a single study from the selected sample, ordered from largest value to smallest. (C) Distribution of studies on the cultural fixation index, where 0 represents USA; (D) Gender Diversity across Studies. Each tick on the x axis represents a single study from the selected sample, ordered from largest value to smallest. Note. Gender diversity: 1 = 100% male; 0 = 100% female.

2.3.1. Reporting of Sample Characteristics

Ethnicity was not specified for 71% of the sample ($n = 5033$). Of the remaining participants, 59% identified as White ($n = 1229$), 13% as Asian ($n = 261$), 11% as Hispanic ($n = 232$), 8% as Other ($n = 163$), 8% as Black ($n = 159$) and 2% as multiracial ($n = 40$; see Figure 4A). A Chi-square goodness of fit test showed ethnicity was unequally distributed in the sample, $\chi^2(5, N = 2084) = 2770, p < .001$. Over half the participants identified as White, with other ethnicities accounting for less than one eighth of the sample. It is important to note, however, almost three quarters of studies failed to report the ethnic composition of their sample, revealing a greater issue of researcher's not reporting demographic information that needs to be tackled.

Education level was not indicated for 33% of individuals ($n = 2382$; Figure 4B). Of the remaining participants, 29% were school-educated ($n = 1383$), 15% were college-educated ($n = 714$), 49% had studied/were studying at university ($n = 2315$), and 7% were currently in/had completed post-graduate studies ($n = 320$; see Figure 10b). In one study, three participants had not received any education (0.06%; this was excluded from the figure). A Chi-square goodness of fit test discovered education levels were unequally distributed in the sample, $\chi^2(3, N = 4735) = 1933, p < .001$, demonstrating a bias towards educated individuals, as almost half of the participants had studied or were studying at university.

The visual status of the participants was not reported for 76% of experiments ($n=101$; Figure 4C). Of the experiments which reported visual status, 47% described using participants with normal or corrected-to-normal vision ($n=15$), 44% specified vision constraints in the exclusion criteria ($n=14$), 6% reported the specific visual test participants completed ($n=2$), and 3% described using participants with generalized vision loss and visual field restriction ($n=1$). Information regarding the participants visual status is generally simple or unclear, and importantly, three quarters of experiments did not report this information.

Figure 4: Participant demographics, separated by (A) ethnicity, (B) education level, (C) visual status; and (D) method of participant remuneration.

2.4. Reporting of Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was not reported for 10% of experiments ($n=13$). For the remaining experiments, 7% were exempt ($n=9$) and 93% were approved ($n=111$; see Figure 5A). All studies received ethical approval from local ethics committees. Note that one experiment did not state which body gave ethical approval (Sattar et al., 2019). Regarding ethical considerations, 78% of experiments reported that participants provided consent ($n=104$), but only 4% stated that participants were informed of their right to withdraw ($n=5$) and 5% acknowledged how they handled data security ($n=6$; see Figure 5B).

Only 15 (12%) experiments specified the use of a scale to identify cybersickness symptoms. Of these, 53% used the Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ; $n=8$), 13% used questions adapted from the SSQ ($n=2$), and 33% used other scales ($n=5$). Only four out of eight experiments using the SSQ reported the SSQ score. The mean score was 4.66 ($SD=3.27$) – symptoms are considered minimal below scores of 10 and negligible for scores below five (Kennedy et al., 1993) – indicating negative side-effects induced by immersions were uncommon in those four studies.

Figure 5: (A) Reporting of participant demographics and (B) information related to ethics in this sample of XR literature ($n=125$ studies). Surprisingly, only a small percentage of studies reported on the visual status of participants, made a record of simulator sickness, or reported on data security within the published manuscript.

2.5. Summary of Results

Overall, the findings of this review suggest there is a considerable lack of diversity and inclusivity in VR and AR research understanding and augmenting human behaviour.

There was a bias in the studies we examined towards Western nations, primarily the USA, followed by the UK and Canada dominated the landscape. This pattern was evident in the location of first and last authors, as well as sample participants, with most participants being WEIRD - like the issues documented in the psychological literature (Henrich et al., 2010). Additionally, consistent with study expectations, the CF_{ST} tool showed the average cultural distance was relatively close to zero, indicating most studies recruited participants from the USA and countries culturally close to the USA.

Although VR and AR research sampled a wide age range of participants, inspection of the data revealed most studies used participants aged between 23 and 32 years. Half of the participants had normal or corrected-to-normal vision and almost half of the participants had no vision problems nor any form of visual impairment based on exclusion criteria. Only one study included participants with generalised vision loss or visual field restriction. In addition, samples tended to be biased towards White ethnicities and educated individuals.

As well as this, almost all VR and AR studies used opportunity sampling, and over one third of studies remunerated participants financially. This recruitment method and remuneration may have generated unrepresentative samples which may not reflect the wider population. As a result of these biases, most participants only represent a small minority of the human population, suggesting VR and AR research understanding human behaviour cannot be generalisable to a wide range of individuals.

It is well known that simulated experiences can cause cybersickness symptoms and, as such, it is important VR and AR studies incorporate a scale examining psychological and physiological after-effects, such as the Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ), to understand how factors, like gender, affect cybersickness. Surprisingly, only one eighth of experiments reported the use of a cybersickness scale and around half of those reported a score on that scale. We recommend that future VR and AR researchers employ a side effect scale as a matter of fact, and subsequently report the score on that scale, to gain a better understanding of the factors influencing cybersickness. In the long term, this could facilitate the development of VR and AR tools which are suitable for all individuals.

2.6. Implications

The findings of the present study have important implications for immersive technology and research. It is imperative future research is more diverse and inclusive to maximise the potential of these. Nielsen et al. (2017) outlined several reasons why most of the population is underrepresented in psychological research; some of which might transfer to VR and AR research. For example, immersive technology can be expensive and research using these tools may not be feasible considering the budgets of many non-Western universities. Western VR and AR researchers could collaborate with academics from diverse geographic countries, which is now more feasible since commercial VR systems can be shared across countries (Peck et al., 2021). Additionally, the CF_{ST} tool (Muthukrishna et al., 2020) could be used to guide researchers to select sites and samples culturally different to each other.

Moreover, VR and AR research samples need to be more inclusive towards adolescents, older adults, different vision abilities, ethnicities other than White and less educated individuals. This is important as novel applications using VR and AR have emerged since recent advances in immersive technology, creating huge opportunities for a wide range of individuals, particularly children (Bortone et

al., 2018). Greater emphasis should be placed on population diversity at all stages of the research process and participants should be actively recruited from outside of authorship universities.

On this note, researchers must aim to use less biased recruitment methods, as opportunity sampling – the most common approach – limits generalisability. However, this could be difficult considering opportunity sampling is less time consuming and more affordable than other methods (Jager et al., 2017). It might be more feasible for academics to improve the credibility of opportunity sampling through other actions, like collecting data in a diversified manner at different days and times, providing detailed descriptions of sample characteristics and avoiding over-generalising results (Stratton, 2021).

Crucially, the review discovered consistent issues with researchers not reporting sample characteristics – particularly ethnicity – which hinders generalisability. This is not just a problem in VR and AR research; psychological research often omits ethnic details regarding samples (Thalmayer et al., 2021). Thus, academics should be more responsible for documenting accurate sample demographic information to increase generalisability. To note, however, some data collection laws in European countries inhibit the collection of ethnic data. Adding to this, data tracking within immersive technology elicits important concerns regarding personal identifiability; one study discovered a VR system correctly identified 95% of users using less than 5 minutes of tracking data per person (Miller et al., 2020), whilst another study showed users could be uniquely identified from over 50,000 users from only 100 seconds of motion with 94% accuracy (Nair et al., 2023). With additional information, such as ethnicity, gender and age, future research may find that data tracking has potential to build user profiles. This would have huge implications for general data protection regulations. It also highlights the importance of reporting ethical considerations, such as privacy and data security, in research articles. Researchers need to find a balance between confidentiality and attempts to describe samples in as much detail as possible, to produce generalisable, whilst ethical, results.

In terms of under-reporting, our results also highlight that VR and AR researchers must become more responsible for reporting important ethical considerations, and their ethical approval status, to ensure the protection of participants as well as the researcher themselves. Researchers also need to record and report more data on side effects to gain a better understanding of cybersickness symptoms in response to immersive technology. Visual status is another important factor in XR, but this too was rarely reported in experiments. Recent research has already highlighted common eye and vision problems which may impact a user's ability to focus on and perceive images in immersive environments, such as uncorrected refractive errors, stereo- and colour vision deficiency (Pladere et al., 2022). If VR and AR research does not report participant visual status information, then researchers will have little knowledge on how different visual abilities respond to immersive technology. Pladere et al. (2022) suggested that the development of a standard eye test, specifically for immersive technology research, could help prevent the exclusion of users with common visual problems as researchers would gain greater insight into how vision impacts VR and AR experiences.

Finally, limited diversity and inclusivity in VR and AR research also has implications concerning technology bias – the unconscious embedding of assumptions, values and opinions, into the development of hardware and software (Peck et al., 2020) – which can result in algorithms producing biased predictions (Mehrabi et al., 2021). The Western bias in XR could increase the degree of technology bias in VR and AR tools, which is critical because technology bias already exists in certain areas of immersive technology, such as HMD designs that are unsupportive of different IPDs and machine learning. For example, face-recognition systems identified light-skinned, males more accurately than dark-skinned, females (Buolamwini & Gebru, 2018), and facial recognition software in digital cameras overpredicted blinking in Asians (Alipourfard et al., 2018). Importantly, machine learning is being incorporated into immersive technology, with applications to augment human behaviour (Wiguna et al., 2020). Therefore, technology bias needs to be addressed to increase the utility of VR and AR. One way to mitigate this bias is by researchers and developers involving diverse populations in the design and testing of VR and AR to ensure suitability to a diverse range of individuals.

2.7. Limitations

The findings of this literature review should be viewed considering some limitations. First, only three databases were searched – two of which were owned by American companies. Article publication in these databases may already be subject to Western bias; research would benefit from including other journals to elucidate the extent of bias in VR and AR research understanding human behaviour. Secondly, the search criteria may have been too strict and database searches only feature published articles – which are often articles with significance (Marks-Anglin & Chen, 2020). Thus, the review may have missed important knowledge, for example information from industry reports. The remainder of this report involves a scoping review of existing frameworks and standards to provide a more complete picture of this landscape.

3. Ethics Methods & Standards for XR

Despite the rapid growth in popularity and ubiquity, XR technologies are still in the early lifecycle of technology-adoption (Statista, 2023). This makes it challenging to recognize the full social impact of the technology. At the same time, it provides us the unique opportunity to understand the security, privacy, health perceptions and practices in XR to proactively influence and shape the future development of technological and design solutions by holistically considering these issues before the technology reaches the majority of the population.

From the technology perspective, concerns about the XR technologies fall into three categories: wellbeing, which includes both the physical (e.g., cybersickness, vision damage, accidents) and psychological (e.g., desensitisation, intensity of experiences, harassment); privacy, how and what data is collected and used; and security. We examined the existing methods & standards and how current XR devices and platforms address these ethical issues. The findings are summarised in the following sections.

3.1. Ethical Technology Assessment (eTA)

Technology Assessment (TA) is a process of assessing the potential benefits, risks, social and economic impacts of a technology. TA aims to predict unintended negative consequences of new technology innovations for informed policy making around the technology. Thus, TA could play an important role in addressing ethical issues related to the development and deployment of new technologies. The fundamental tenet of any TA is that the technology should be developed keeping the end users in mind. However, the main challenge with various TA frameworks is that they are resource intensive and don't specifically address the ethical issues of new technology development. Currently, no specific standards exist for the ethical assessment of XR technologies. Therefore, there is a need for a framework to identify the potential ethical issues while developing the XR technology and applications. Ethical Technology Assessment (eTA) is one such framework to find and characterise the ethical aspects of an emerging technology (Palm & Hansson, 2006). Based on the checklist for the early warning system for ethical implications of new technologies proposed by Palm & Hansson (2006), we have selected the following ethical aspects relevant for XR technologies:

- (i) Dissemination and use of information
- (ii) Control, influence, and power
- (iii) Impact on social contact patterns
- (iv) Privacy
- (v) Gender, minorities, and justice
- (vi) Impact on human values

When it comes to human values, privacy, autonomy, liberty, and justice have been identified as core values in relation to information and communication technologies (ICT) (Brey, 2000). XR being the

advanced ICT, key issues from ICT ethics such as privacy, security, intellectual property, consent, cyberbullying, and digital divide are applicable for XR, in addition to the relevant health ethics specific for XR devices. Based on this, we have identified the following as the key criteria for the ethical technology assessment of XR technology.

Informed Consent: XR systems collect sensitive information such as eye tracking, health, and biometric information. An informed consent, therefore, is a prerequisite before collecting such information. Users should be provided with clear and concise information about the XR experience, including the risks and benefits, before asking for user consent.

Privacy and Security: XR systems collect and process a wide range of user data. Security measures should be implemented to protect the user data and users should be informed about the collected data and how it is used.

Transparency: XR technologies should be transparent about how they work and how they affect users.

Accessibility: XR technologies must be accessible to all users regardless of their physical, cognitive, or sensory abilities.

Content Standards: XR technologies could be used to create immersive and engaging experiences, but this also raises concerns about the appropriateness of the content. The XR content should not promote hatred, violence, or discrimination.

Fairness: XR technologies should not be used to maintain or amplify social inequalities. The technology should be fair to all population and not discriminate any groups or minorities.

Social Responsibility: XR technologies have the potential to impact society in significant ways (McVeigh-Schultz & Isbister, 2021). The broader social impact of XR technologies should be considered and necessary steps should be taken to minimize any negative consequences.

Ethical TA is an iterative process with 3-part assessment containing: (i) a set of ethical questions covering various ethical aspects and implications of new technology anchored in relevant values and principles, (ii) an ethical matrix with relevant values and stakeholders for ethical assessment, and (iii) a general ethical reflection (Palm et al., 2013). The eTA questionnaire and ethical matrix are adapted and updated with the relevant ethical criteria for XR technologies (see Appendix). This questionnaire and ethical matrix will be further developed and utilised for the XR users' ethics awareness and rating system in the upcoming work deliverables.

3.2 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

In addition to the eTA, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM 3, 3rd version) 28.04.2023 23:26:00 addresses sociotechnical aspects both from the higher-level design and development perspective (what human centred requirements should be considered in technology design and development before being released on the market), and from the users' hands-on practical perspective (how users perceive and experience the technology while using it). Rooted in the Theory of Reasoned Action (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975) and Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), TAM focuses on four main outputs toward technology acceptance and consequently adoption that are: (i) perceived usefulness, (ii) perceived ease of use, (iii) readiness toward technology (i.e., behaviour intentions to use a given technology) and finally (iv) usage of technology (i.e., user behaviour). A variety of constructs and their relationships support these four main outputs. In this study, the initial TAM focus on computers is adapted for XR:

- Subjective norms (social influence towards using XR technology)
- Experience (own's experience with XR technology)
- Voluntariness (own's free will to use XR technology)
- Image (perception that using XR technology will enhance own status within a given social system)

- Job relevance (belief that XR technology is applicable for performing the job or activity)
- Output quality (belief that the using XR technology performs well for the task or activity at hand)
- Result demonstrability (belief that the results of using XR technology are explicit, tangible and communicable)
- Self-efficacy (belief in own ability to perform a task or activity while using XR technology)
- Perceptions of external control (perception of community resources and support for facilitating the usage of XR technology)
- Anxiety (degree of apprehension or fear when faced with using XR technology)
- Playfulness (the degree of cognitive spontaneity when using XR technology)
- Perceived enjoyment (the extent to which using XR technology is perceived enjoyable per se, independently of performance)
- Objective usability (actual level of effort for completing tasks or activities with XR technology)

TAM 3 is one of the mainstream models and methods used for sociotechnical assessment. TAM 3 was already used for assessing VR technology and applications in safety-critical scenarios for radiation protection training in the nuclear industry (Pancotti, 2020), and it will be adapted and applied for leveraging essential ethic aspects related to XR in the current study.

3.3. Existing Ethical Standards for XR

There are sets of rules and guidelines for ethical behaviour in XR technology development and usage set up by open-source communities (Open AR), non-profit organisations (XRSI) and technical professional organisations (IEEE).

The Open AR Cloud Code of Conduct (CoC) (<https://www.openarcloud.org/documents/code-of-conduct>) outlines the expected behaviour of individuals participating in the Open AR Cloud community. It emphasizes the values of inclusivity, respect, and collaboration, and prohibits any form of harassment, discrimination, or inappropriate behaviour. The CoC encourages individuals to report any incidents of inappropriate behaviour and outlines the steps that will be taken to address such incidents and states that violating the code of conduct may result in consequences such as expulsion from the community. The CoC is inspired by and attributed to (*Contributor Covenant*; n.d.) and (*Community Participation Guidelines – Mozilla*, n.d.).

The XR Safety Initiative (XRSI) has published a CoC for XR technology (XRSI, 2020), outlining the ethical guidelines for developers, users, and organizations (<https://xrsi.org/xrsi-code-of-conduct>). The CoC includes principles such as prioritizing user safety and well-being, ensuring privacy and security, promoting inclusivity and accessibility, and avoiding the perpetuation of harmful stereotypes and biases. The code also emphasizes the importance of transparency and accountability; encourages ongoing evaluation and improvement of XR technology to ensure it is used in a responsible and ethical manner. The XRSI CoC is attributed to Open AR Cloud CoC, contributor Covenant & Mozilla community participation guides.

The IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) has published a set of whitepapers addressing various ethical issues through its Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (<https://standards.ieee.org/industry-connections/ethics-extended-reality/>). The whitepaper on ethics, diversity, inclusion, and accessibility in the development and use of XR technology (Fox & Thornton, 2022) includes recommendations for addressing ethical considerations related to technology, such as ensuring privacy, security, and transparency. It also provides guidance on promoting diversity and inclusion in technology development, and addressing accessibility concerns to ensure that technology is accessible to all individuals, regardless of their abilities. The guidance document emphasizes the importance of ongoing evaluation and improvement of technology to ensure that it is developed and used in a responsible and

ethical manner that promotes equity and social responsibility. The IEEE whitepaper on XR and the erosion of Anonymity and Privacy (McGill, 2021) discusses the key privacy challenges introduced by XR, the shortcomings of existing rights and legislation to address these issues and provide recommendations for protection and mitigation of XR-enabled digital harm. The IEEE whitepaper on social VR and trolling, harassment and online safety outlines the safety issues in social and multi-user metaverses and provide guidelines for ethical interaction design (Mangina & Eleni, 2021). Another white paper in the series discusses the ownership of digital identity and virtual clones, concerns and risks associated with virtual clones, and provides initial recommendations for addressing this issue (Eriksson, 2021). In addition, IEEE has published industry specific whitepapers on XR ethics in Medicine (Evans, 2022), Education (Eleni Mangina, 2021), Business, Finance and Economics (Middleton, 2022). These whitepapers layout the ethical concerns specific for the XR applications in different domains and provide initial set of recommendations and guidelines for initiating the process of a policy on standards to address XR ethics issues. Metaverse governance challenges and recommendations are dealt with in the Metaverse and its Governance (2022). The sustainable metaverse should be aligned with United Nations' 17 sustainable goals through the identification and implementation of norms in an international societal governance system spanning countries, governments, institutions, companies, and individuals. The proposed recommendations focus on creating systems process for governance, cascade societal or rule-based interventions with governmental legislation, legal resources, and privacy.

Overall, the IEEE metaverse whitepapers are a solid foundation for ongoing ethics considerations related to the metaverse.

3.4. Law enforcement in XR

In addition to XR standards and guidelines, the current expansion of the metaverse and its accompanying technologies has raised complex ethical concerns regarding law enforcement in the metaverse. Indeed, law enforcement is a completely different stage compared to only providing community guidelines and mediation in the metaverse platforms. Two key reports, one from Interpol (2022) and another from Europol's Innovation Lab (2022), highlight the growing and novel potential of cybercrime, fraud, and other illegal activities within virtual worlds. They also emphasize the difficulties faced by law enforcement agencies to define what criminal activities are in the metaverse compared to the real world (such as physical aspects compared to virtual ones), and consequently in dealing with offenders, given among other factors the adaptation to the metaverse of current real world legal crime definitions, the anonymous nature of user interactions, cross-jurisdictional issues, and the use of cryptocurrencies for transactions.

One of the most pressing ethical concerns in the metaverse is balancing the need for effective policing with the protection of individual privacy rights. Additionally, the metaverse transcends geographical boundaries, complicating the application of traditional jurisdictional rules and potentially requiring new international legal frameworks for virtual spaces. The potential for increased surveillance within the metaverse could also lead to concerns about abuse of power and infringement of civil liberties, necessitating careful implementation of law enforcement practices in the metaverse.

These reports emphasise that addressing these emerging complex ethical challenges will require the development of new legal frameworks, technological innovations, and collaborative efforts between public and private sector entities. Collaboration between law enforcement agencies and private sector organizations that develop and maintain virtual worlds will be essential for effective policing. Indeed, most of the crime categories identified in the Interpol and Europol reports are similar to the definitions of inappropriate behavior in the community standards, guidelines and conditions of use emphasized by metaverse platform providers. However, this collaboration raises ethical questions about the appropriate and efficient level of involvement and influence these companies should have over policing efforts within their platforms. Furthermore, ensuring equal access to justice in the metaverse is critical. These reports recommend that law enforcement agencies must address barriers for certain individuals and groups, such

as those with limited access to technology or disabilities that hinder their ability to engage with virtual worlds, to maintain accessible and equitable justice for all users.

4. Review of ethics in existing XR solutions

4.1. Metaverses and Social XR Platforms

Metaverses are platforms providing tools and services for building, deploying, and using digital assets such as 3D models, virtual avatars with social and interactive features that enable users to create, host and interact within virtual worlds. Currently, metaverse platforms come in different forms such as desktop/mobile application (e.g., Secondlife, Roblox), XR headset based (e.g., VRChat) or web-based (e.g., Onland) services. Three main categories of metaverses are identified: consumer metaverse, enterprise metaverse and industrial metaverse (MIT Technology Review, 2022). While the three categories share many features, the consumer metaverse focuses mostly on XR entertainment and games, the enterprise metaverse focuses on XR collaboration solutions, and the industrial metaverse proposes additional features such as interoperability and high-fidelity digital twins and simulation features, in line with Industry 4.0 and 5.0 efforts.

Examples of available metaverses and Social XR platforms are provided in Table 1 under consumer, enterprise, and industrial applications categories. A word cloud representing text extracted from 12 metaverses indicating the key themes in these documents can be seen in **Figure 6**.

Table 1 Metaverse examples per category

Consumer	Enterprise	Industrial
Secondlife VRChat Decentraland Roblox Fortnite Minecraft Somnium space Onland Spatial vTime XR Mozilla Hubs Meta Horizon Worlds AltspaceVR (shutdown 10.03.23)	Immersed Glue VR MeetinVR Virbela EON Reality Meta Horizon workrooms	Omniverse

SteamVR, Windows Mixed Reality, PlayStation VR, Meta Horizon Worlds, HTC Viveverse, Spatial, Mozilla Hubs, Virbela, VRChat are among current prominent XR social and application platforms. To address ethics topics, most of the platform owners/product developers have established conditions of use, community standards or community guidelines for using the platforms. These platforms address similar concerns. Generally, they outline behaviours that are not acceptable, such as harassment, discrimination, or offensive language, and encourage contributors to treat others with respect and professionalism. They provide guidelines on how to report inappropriate behaviour or content to the platform moderators, and some of them outline the steps that should be taken to address such incidents. In addition, they provide information on how to protect user privacy and safety, such as using strong passwords and two-factor authentication. In short, generic concerns for online usage are provided, but XR specific ethics aspects should be better emphasized. An example of good communication of ethics was AltspaceVR (belonging to Microsoft and shut down on March 10, 2023). Compared to other platforms where ethics aspects are presented in fine print on the bottom of their main webpage, AltspaceVR provided ethics considerations in the most explicit way on the lefthand side menu on their website. 'User safety and moderation' was the 4th topic addressed on the 1st level of the menu. This topic contained guidelines related to safety tools (space bubble, muting oneself or others, block other avatars, quick exit to title screen, sending a report, reporting an event or a whole world). Furthermore, health and safety topics (VR sickness, hardware and software nausea reduction, motion sickness reduction) were addressed under the Troubleshooting & support FAQ. Community standards (defamation and intolerance, harassment, cyberbullying and intimidation, lewd or unwanted advances, discovery and disclosure of personal information, impersonation of an AltspaceVR employee, inappropriate content, personal space, alternate accounts for harassing other users, reporting violations of community standards) were provided under the Terms and standards menu entry.

4.1.1 Privacy policies

One of the goals of the privacy policies is to achieve transparency around data-collection with end-users. Much like the CoCs, most XR solution providers have similar privacy policies mentioned on their websites. There is a general statement about how these platforms will collect, use, and store personal information to provide their products and services. Privacy policies also highlight that the collected user data will not be shared with third-party companies, and what type of data is shared with whom when required by law. Privacy policies provide details on how users can access, update, or delete their data. Additionally, they include details on how these platforms use cookies and other tracking technologies, as well as how they protect user data from unauthorized access or misuse. They also provide details on how users can contact them if they have any concerns or questions about their privacy policies.

One of the main challenges for privacy in XR is the lack of user awareness of the sensitivity, nature and volume of the collected data (Warin & Reinhardt, 2022). Earlier studies show that privacy policies are difficult to comprehend, often not read by common users and generally don't support rational decision-making (McDonald & Cranor, 2008). With these challenges, privacy policies may not be effective for achieving the goal of transparency around data-collection with end-users (Adams et al., 2018). Despite being one of the easiest ways to establish developer-user transparency, the current ecosystem of XR privacy policies might not achieve this goal. XRSI in its privacy framework (XRSI, 2020) tries to address these issues through a baseline set of standards, guidelines, and best practices for achieving better privacy, transparency and trust in XR platforms. However, this is not yet a standard.

Another XR specific privacy goal is related to proxemics in the extended reality environments (intimate, personal, social and public distances) and their common acceptability. For example, proxemics is implemented in Meta Horizons as a personal bubble with a radius of 2 feet, as a measure against harassment (this feature was also provided in AltspaceVR).

4.1.2 Accessibility

Digital accessibility that works for users with disabilities in general is an important concern for wider adaptability of XR. Currently, accessibility features and guidance for the developers aren't available for making universal XR applications in the existing platforms. There is an ongoing work at the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) to develop standards for accessibility in XR environments by creating Common Access Profiles (CAP) for XR, but the ISO standards development is still at an early phase (Funka, 2021).

Since XR requires various human senses (predominantly vision, hearing, touch senses and smell in rare cases), cognitive and motor skills for providing immersive experiences, disabilities in some of these senses and/or mobility will impact how users experience in XR. On the other hand, XR is also promoted as assistive technologies to solve some of the accessibility challenges. Assistive technology (AT) are solutions created expressly to assist persons with disabilities in their daily lives. XR technologies are currently employed in several assistive technology solutions for persons with vision, hearing impairments and mobility challenges (e.g., eSight, WalkingVR, ARcaptions). The University of Melbourne has mapped the pros and cons of XR technology for users with different disabilities to outline the accessibility challenges and opportunities for XR (<https://www.unimelb.edu.au/accessibility/virtual-reality>). Started in partnership with Cornell University, the XR Access Initiative (Home | XR Access Initiative) provides a strategy (XR Access 2020+ Strategy - Final Version (Slides) - Google Slides) for XR requirements, design and practices for enabling people with disabilities to use XR. Companies such as Vision Buddy (VisionBuddy | Vision Buddy - Television Watching for Visually Impaired) and Give Vision (SightPlus (givevision.net)) are focusing on providing VR assistive solutions for visually impaired people. The AR for visually impaired people (<https://drfoxdesign.com/ar-for-vips>) focused on indoor navigation. Furthermore, latest XR devices such as the HTC Vive XR Elite and Meta Quest offer glasses-free features for users with vision issues, the former providing diopter adjustments from 0 to -6 (<https://www.vive.com/us/product/vive-xr-elite/overview/>), and the latter providing prescription lenses (Quest 2 Virtuclear™ Lens Insert | Meta Quest | Meta Store).

Safety

Safety aspects are the most present in the various metaverses, platforms and device user guides. They are prominent especially during the initial steps for setting up XR headsets. Indeed, user safety is addressed as a mandatory step, in which users need to consider usage parameters such as configuring their safe physical space for the XR device. However, such safety features need to be searched for since they are not emphasized on the main pages of XR platforms and metaverses. They are either in fine print or at the bottom of the main webpage (e.g., Meta Horizon Worlds, or nested within the overall site webpages).

4.1.3 XR development platforms

Unity 3D, Unreal

Unity 3D and Unreal Engine are among the main development tools for creating 3D content. They both have application markets where solution developers can download and install a variety of packages, libraries, and plugins to use and integrate in their XR applications. No code of conduct or other related ethics aspects (safety, privacy ratings, etc.) could be found on the main pages of their application markets. Such aspects are addressed by each asset provider and can be found on links from the application market to the asset provider. For example, in the Unity Asset store, the Oculus Integration package provides a link to Meta's website where, as mentioned earlier, the user must scroll to the bottom of the main page to finally find safety, privacy, community standards, etc. in fine print.

Generative AI for XR

Recently, AI and ML libraries and tools became accessible in the overall market and for XR. While for example the ML Agents library has been available for Unity 3D since 2020, ChatGPT and equivalent libraries and tools are very recent. Among a variety of possible applications, the main ones related to XR

are the generative creation of virtual worlds (script or code generation) and the generative application to XR avatars (physical appearance, interactive features, movements, speech, lip sync, voice, etc.). Furthermore, avatar interoperability across metaverses (i.e., having the same avatar in various worlds) is a recent feature proposed by Ready Player Me (Takahashi, 2023). While such AI and ML are very promising, they can also generate XR unsuitable content (e.g., distorted, fake, misleading, impersonating, etc.). It is therefore necessary from the ethics perspective to tackle the usage of such generative content in XR, especially from the perspective of 3rd party integration in XR design and development. Indeed, it is important for XR solution providers to assess AI and ML and endorse accountability when integrating such 3rd party libraries and tools in their products. This topic is related to both practical aspects (e.g., XR development) and metaverse governance and legal aspects (e.g., EU and worldwide institutions that decide who should be accountable in terms of ethics).

4.1.4 XR devices

Headsets

Oculus Quest 2, HTC Vive Pro 2, Valve Index, HP Reverb G2, Pico 4, PlayStation VR, Meta Quest and Quest pro, Varjo XR-3, Microsoft HoloLens 2 are some of the most popular XR headsets currently available on the market. The current state of the art of XR HMDs has improved significantly in terms of display technology (e.g., higher resolution, improved color, and contrast, lense technologies, wider FOV, varifocal displays), latency (e.g., higher refresh rate), graphic processing (e.g., foveated rendering) and connectivity (tethered, untethered, standalone) compared to the devices even from a few years ago. The comfort of these devices has also improved through better ergonomic, lightweight designs, adjustable interpupillary distances (IPD), better ventilation, etc. Many of these improvements, combined have contributed to more immersive experiences and better wearability of the devices for extended periods of time. Despite the improvements, the challenges related to resolution (full natural resolution is not achieved), comfort (devices are still bulky and cumbersome to wear for prolonged periods), accessibility (disability support) are not fully addressed yet and still a work in progress.

Interaction controllers

Hand-held controllers are the most common type of interaction controllers used in VR. They are usually designed to fit comfortably in the user's hands and have buttons, triggers, and joysticks that allow the user to interact with the virtual environment. Many of the handheld controllers also include haptic sensors and actuators that detect the user's touch and respond by providing haptic feedback.

Gesture controllers are other type of controllers that use the user's hand and body movements to control the virtual environment. They include sensors that track the user's movements and translate them into actions within the virtual environment. Screen based AR application utilise touch gestures in general.

Eye-tracking controllers use the user's eye movements to control the virtual environment. Eye tracking sensors track the user's gaze and translate it into actions within the virtual environment.

Face tracking features are a current XR trend for translating facial expressions into user's emotion detection and avatar animation (VIVE Facial Tracker, Meta Quest tech specs).

Voice controllers use the user's voice to control the virtual environment. They recognize the user's commands through their voice inputs and translates them into actions within the virtual environment.

Brain computer interfaces (BCI) devices use users' electroencephalography (EEG) for controlling and interacting with virtual environments. They include sensors that capture users' brainwaves and software that filters, categorizes them, and plugins that translate EEG into actions within the virtual environment. Recent integration efforts of BCI with XR are carried out currently by Varjo and OpenBCI (2022).

Wearables (e.g., wristbands – Meta, XR gloves – HaptX, Magnus Prime X) and full or partial body motion capture and interaction devices (e.g., Xsens, Teslasuit, Skinetic haptic vest, OWO "all sensations" vest) enable to track users' body segments and joints and provide enhanced natural avatar animation as

well as interaction features within the XR worlds. Such systems capture a huge amount of user data, and therefore such solution providers explicitly mention privacy policies relative to product usage.

Locomotion platforms

In addition, XR developments focus also on locomotion devices such as cybershoes (e.g., KAT VR Loco) and omnidirectional treadmills (e.g., KAT VR Walk, Cyberith Virtualizer, Virtuix Omni One and Arena). These devices provide several usage modes, from beginner to expert, and safety is one of the main aspects that is specifically considered by such solution providers.

5. Synthesis & Further Requirements

The literature and technology reviews performed in this report show that there is much room for improvement when it comes to the ethical aspects (e.g., privacy, safety, accessibility) of XR research. Our literature review demonstrated that very few studies report on fundamental ethical issues and our technology review suggested that efforts are required for consolidating XR guidelines and their implementation and possible enforcement in the EU XR solution providers community.

The ethical technology assessment (eTA) and technology acceptance model (TAM) provide an initial framework for capturing the essential XR ethics aspects and make them actionable for both assessing and designing and developing XR solutions for both early adopters and advanced XR users. This framework needs to be further integrated and tailored for various XR use cases in terms of construct relevance and criticality, e.g., data security may be more critical in health and education settings than in other settings.

The review of the various standardization efforts provides a good overview of the ethics aspects that need to be addressed, as well as of the guidelines and recommendations to be further consolidated.

Ethics aspects are present in metaverses, XR portals, development platforms, and XR devices, however unequally. While metaverses and XR portals provide community standards and guidelines that are to some extent easier to understand by non-specialist users, the development platforms, and their application markets, as well as the XR devices are more focused in terms of use from a technical and legal perspective. Furthermore, the ethics aspects are not salient and even may seem optional in the way they are presented and communicated to users, meaning that users may completely overlook these aspects when they use XR. Except for safety aspects that are provided in the initial XR device set-up menus at runtime in the XR headsets, the other ethics related aspects are conveyed traditionally on websites that are disconnected from the XR devices, so the way ethics aspects are communicated to users doesn't seem efficient. Furthermore, the various information is organized as weblinks under chapters, creating information overload even for users interested and taking their time to process such information. Currently it seems that XR solution providers are blending information from their traditional websites with information specific to XR (e.g., Meta links from Meta Horizon Worlds to Meta Facebook community standards). There are also discrepancies on the various websites of a same company. For example, on the website of Meta Venues, parental guidance is very salient on the main webpage, while on Meta Horizon Worlds it is not.

Ethics aspects are not present on application markets. If users want to find out about an application provider, they need to go the extra step and check the application provider's website to find out more about the provider and the application. Some of the application providers are offering blockchain for the transactions (e.g., Viverse), some provide user reviews for their applications (e.g., SteamVR).

Collectively, our findings emphasize the need for a unified approach to ethics across metaverses, XR portals, and platforms. This can be achieved by effectively and comprehensibly communicating ethical considerations to XR users, integrating critical ethics aspects as safety features directly into the XR headsets, and incorporating ethics ratings into XR devices and applications. This would allow both solution providers and users to contribute to raising awareness of ethical considerations during actual usage. A

comprehensive ethics guideline, accommodating both current XR users and potential future adopters, is crucial for promoting transparency, user safety, and privacy protection. By fostering collaboration between industry stakeholders, policymakers, and users, this guideline can create a culture of shared responsibility and ethical awareness in the rapidly evolving XR landscape. Implementing such guidelines is a crucial step in addressing the ethical challenges posed by the rapid growth of this sector, supporting responsible development and use of XR technologies for the benefit of all users.

Finally, this report primarily examines the ethical issues associated with XR solutions. However, it is essential to recognize that there are valuable lessons to be learned from a broader societal sustainability standpoint, particularly in the context of the volatile XR market. As these technologies become increasingly integrated into society, addressing ethical concerns from this wider perspective will be crucial to ensure responsible and sustainable growth in the XR industry. The closure of XR companies, XR teams within companies (see Microsoft and Meta), or even XR platforms (e.g., AltspaceVR) and support for devices (e.g., Google Daydream, Google Glass), can have a considerable impact on both public and private XR communities. These closures are often announced abruptly, for example the shutdown of AltspaceVR shocked its community, even though other XR portals like Spatial offered ways to transfer existing assets and worlds. While this technology is in its infancy, such events can be a source of frustration and inconvenience for early adopters (beyond the obvious impact on staff working at these companies/on these products affected by these closures), the impact of this type of event could be catastrophic for those users who rely on, or are required to use, these technologies for work and school and risk confidence in the sector in the medium term.

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APPENDIX

Systematic Search Details

Search Terms

Table S 1: *Keyword Combinations for Literature Search*

Set 1 (OR)		Set 2 (OR)
Virtual reality	AND	Learn*
Augmented reality		Train*
Extended reality		Teach*
Virtual environment		Educat*
Virtual reality headset		Treat*
Head mounted display		Assess*
Head mounted device		Therap*
HMD		Skill*
360 degrees		Perform*
		Ability*

Inclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria for the articles were: (1) articles reported the use of VR or AR; (2) the device used to display VR or AR must be head-mounted; (3) the device must display 3D information; (4) the device must allow interaction with 3D objects; (5) articles that use mobile VRs (e.g., Google Cardboard), high-end HMDs (e.g., Oculus Rift) or enhanced VRs (e.g., Cave Automatic Virtual Environment); (6) articles targeted towards understanding or augmenting human behaviour; (7) the article title must contain the key words 'virtual reality' or 'augmented reality' (to restrict the search to the most relevant studies). The following exclusion criteria were also used to screen the articles: (1) study type (e.g., systematic reviews, meta-analyses, study protocol, review articles or other non-empirical articles); (2) abstract only source; (3) non-human population; (4) no or unclear use of VR or AR requiring HMD; (5) articles not related to understanding or augmenting human behaviour.

Selection Process

The initial search yielded a total of 1,696 studies. After the removal of duplicates, 1,270 studies underwent title and abstract screening against the eligibility criteria. Following this, 964 studies were excluded, leaving 306 full-text articles to be assessed. During this stage, 181 studies were removed due to the following reasons: no or unclear use of HMD; the study was not designed in any way that could augment human behaviour and/or performance; the study was a review article, systematic review, or study protocol; no full text was available; the study used animals. A final sample of 125 studies were included in the full review.

Data Extraction

The following data were extracted from the selected studies:

- Study characteristics: author, year, title, journal, digital objective identifier (DOI), key words, first author institute location, last author institute location, recruitment method, remuneration, ethical approval, and ethical considerations.
- Immersive technology characteristics: VR or AR, HMD platform, side effects scale, and side effects scale score.

- Participant characteristics: total sample recruited, total sample analysed, reasons for exclusion, age, gender, ethnicity, visual status, level of education and location of recruitment.

A pilot-test using ten articles from a preliminary systematic search of VR and AR literature confirmed the data extraction categories were suitable for the purpose of this study. Studies which involved multiple experiments were extracted as separate studies. When studies were missing data for certain categories, the following adjustments were made: (1) for studies which did not report key words, alternative key words were obtained from online databases (e.g., “mesh terms” from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>); (2) for studies which did not mention the nationality of the sample, but all authors were from a single country, it was inferred that the sample was from the same nation (for mixed-nationality authors in five studies, it was impossible to determine); (3) for studies which did not report any data on age, the sample’s age range was taken from the inclusion criteria if this was available; (4) when gender and ethnicity were only reported as percentage values, the percentages were converted to raw numbers; (5) for studies which did not explicitly state the level of education of their participants, it was inferred from the participant’s occupation when possible; (6) when studies did not specify the HMD platform used, it was inferred from the paper that the study involved a HMD and 3D interaction (Chang et al., 2021 - figure 1; Chang et al., 2021 - figure 1; Kim & Chun, 2022 - figure 1; Liao et al., 2019 - figure 1; Pozeg et al., 2017 - figure 1A; Teodoro-Vite et al., 2021 - figure 1B).

Additionally, the last authors of six studies were affiliated with institutions from more than one nation; in these cases, both locations were included. In two studies, gender was misreported (Miehlbradt et al., 2021) and mistyped (Chiang et al., 2022) for one group of participants, and this was impossible to report. Another study reported over half of their participants were aged 21 to 25 years, but the full age range of participants could not be determined (Havola et al., 2021). Finally, one study reported their sample was primarily Caucasian (Real et al., 2017), however, with no raw numbers it was impossible to determine the number of participants. All data was extracted to Microsoft Excel (version 2202).

Data Synthesis

For recruitment method, studies which used volunteer and convenience samples to recruit participants were combined into one category defined as “opportunity”; this consisted of any study which recruited people from the target population who were available at the time and willing to take part. For studies which reported participant information only in terms of their intervention group, the information was grouped together for each study as follows: values for gender, ethnicity and level of education were summed together, and average values were calculated for mean age and standard deviation (six studies reported median age and interquartile range and were excluded from calculations). The ethnicities reported across the studies were grouped into six categories: White (including Caucasian); Hispanic (including Latin American); Black (including African American); Asian (including Asian American, Asian Indian, American Indian, Chinese, Han Chinese, Korean, Middle Eastern, South Asian, Southeast Asian, West Asian); other (including Asian American Caucasian, Hispanic Caucasian, Black/Asian/Mixed, Hawaiian, Non-white, Non-British); not specified. HMD platforms were grouped into the following categories: Oculus (including Oculus Rift, Oculus Go, Oculus Quest); HTC Vive; Samsung Gear VR; Microsoft HoloLens; eMagin (including eMagin z800); nVisor (including nVisor ST50, nVisor SX111); Merge VR; Google Cardboard; other (including Cardboard Goggles, Company S, Dell Visor Windows Mixed Reality Headset, Epson Moverio BT-200 Smart Glasses, Magic Leap 1, the OCTAVE Facility, Oncomfort, OssoVR, Pico Goblin VR, RITECH II, Sony, Stereoscopic Glasses, Tzumi Dream Vision VR, and Viewmaster VR). Data was coded into a format compatible with statistical analysis software.

Ethical questionnaire

Questions related to privacy

What types of information, if any, do you consider intrusive? Why?

Are certain ways of using the technology/applications considered privacy sensitive/invasive? If so, what ways/applications and why?

Are you aware of how your data is processed?

Are you aware of who have access to your data?

Who has/should have access to the information generated by XR device and why?

Are there any aspects of using XR technology that you consider embarrassing?

Questions related to trust, safety and security

Do you feel safer with the technology than before it was implemented?

Does the perceived safety correspond with the security/actual reliability?

Is the reliability sufficient for the aim the technology should fill?

Questions related to informed consent

How is the XR technology/application presented?

In what way, if at all, did you consent to using the XR technology/application?

Were you sufficiently informed prior to your consent?

Are you aware of how the technology functions?

Are you aware of the consequences of your acceptance?

Are there aspects of the technology/system that you are uncertain of/would like more information about?

Would you like reminders regarding a ubiquitous/continuously active system?

Do you have the chance to opt out?

Do you feel that you are forced to consent?

Questions related to need and functionality

What is the aim of the XR technology/application?

What problem does the XR technology/application solve?

Is the aim laudable/reasonable?

Is the technology a good/the best means given that aim?

What need does the technology correspond to?

What need does the user have?

Does the technology correspond to this need?

How should the technology be designed/implemented in order to correspond to the need?

How is the technology marketed/launched?

Questions related to autonomy/transparency

Have you been involved in the development and/or implementation of the technology? If so, have you been able to influence the design/usage of the technology?

Do you feel a need to adjust to the technology? In what way?

Do you know what the system is doing and why?

Do you know how to control the system in different usage situations?

Does the technology enhance independence? If so, in what way?

Questions related to accessibility and fairness

To what extent is the technology distributed fairly?

To what extent can the technology be fairly distributed?

Does it imply a “digital divide”/“ information divide” – a gap between have and have nots?

Should the technology be used to even out inequalities stemming from “the natural lottery”?

Ethical Matrix

The ethical matrix consists of values to be realised and stakeholders. The matrix is used for identifying ethical problems among different stakeholders. To be useful in clarifying, accommodating, or solving ethical problems the values outlined in the matrix must be specified and balanced regarding specific stakeholders in specific contexts.

Values to be realised	Stakeholders				
	Users	Technology facilitators	Policy makers	Regulators	Technology developers
Privacy (of data)					
Ownership of data					
Privacy by respect for a private sphere (local, physical, mental)					
Autonomy/Freedom of choice					
Security and safety					
Informed consent					
Fairness					
Satisfaction of the individual needs and preferences (Utility)					
Social relations					
Robustness					
Ease of use					
Affordability					
Cost-effectiveness					